

Validation of a Contactless Motion Monitoring System for Home-Based Rehabilitation

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Abstract—Due to the growing interest in non-invasive technologies for assessing motor performance, particularly within the context of home-based rehabilitation of elderly individuals, this study aims to validate a novel contactless sensorized pad for motion monitoring at home. Ten healthy volunteers were recruited to perform two lower limb exercises, with simultaneous data collection from a gold standard motion capture system and the sensorized pad. The performance was assessed through error metrics in time and space domains, enabling a comparison of pad accuracy and reliability in tracking movements.

Index Terms—home-based rehabilitation, elderly exercises, motion monitoring, smart pad

I. INTRODUCTION

Non-invasive devices for assessing motor performance have gained attention, also in the field of home-based rehabilitation. Such technologies are useful for addressing the growing demand for remote healthcare solutions, especially for people who may have limited access to in-person rehabilitation services [1]. The ability to remotely monitor motor performance is essential for elderly people, since regular physical activity can have a positive impact on active aging and its associated benefits, including improved physical health, enhanced mobility and independence, cognitive improvements, emotional well-being, and better sleep [2]. Several studies use Motion CAPture (MOCAP) systems or magneto-inertial sensors as reference benchmarks to validate contactless sensors for movement assessment [3], [4]. Notably, markerless MOCAP systems (using RGB cameras and webcams) can be employed for the monitoring of kinematic parameters. The performance metrics commonly employed to validate new devices typically include error metrics such as Maximum Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Coefficient of Multiple Correlation (CMC), Limits of Agreement (LoA), and Mean Percentage Absolute Error (MAPE), depending on the specific study objectives and the characteristics of the device under testing [5]. In this scenario, our objective is to validate

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a novel contactless sensorized pad for motion monitoring, specifically designed to assist elderly individuals during home-based motor exercises for active aging. In line with available scientific literature, our approach follows a validation model that uses a MOCAP system as a benchmarking device, allowing for a comparative evaluation.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Experimental setup

The device to be validated consists of a sensorized pad, made of three aligned boards, each one integrating 32 capacitive sensors arranged in a checkerboard pattern. The sensors are developed with HEXTRASENSE technology, that aims to detect distance and proximity. A graphical user interface allows the login to the database and the exercise selection. A MOCAP system from BTS Bioengineering was employed as benchmarking device for validation. This system consists of 8 infrared cameras (acquisition frequency of 60 Hz) and 2 force plates (acquisition frequency of 240 Hz). Markers were placed according to the Davis protocol.

Fig. 1. Picture of the experimental setup.

A trigger module was adopted to synchronously collect data from both the systems during the exercises.

B. Evaluation metrics

Three indexes were used to evaluate the pad performance: (i) Execution Time (ET): it is the time taken by participants to complete each exercise; (ii) RMSE: it is the degree of discrepancy between the detected movement rates \hat{y}_i and the reference data y_i . It is computed as $RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}$, where N is the number of observations (i.e. repetitions for each exercise); (iii) Δ_{CoP} : it is the difference between the Center of Pressure (CoP) calculated with the two systems. For the BTS MOCAP the CoP is automatically calculated by the system as the point where the resultant force acts on the force plates; for the sensorized pad it is determined as the spatial coordinates of the midpoint, weighted based on the signal amplitudes from the capacitive sensors.

C. Experimental protocol

To pursue the objective of the work the exercises defined in the protocol were simultaneously recorded by using both the ground-truth system (BTS MOCAP system) and the sensorized pad. The experimental protocol includes two tasks for the lower limb (T1 and T2), chosen among the exercises to be performed at home for maintaining mobility suggested by the Italian Society of Gerontology and Geriatrics:

- T1: starting from a standing position, the participant was asked to stand up on the toes and return to start position for 30 times;
- T2: starting from a sitting position with both feet on the floor, the participant had to lift one foot off the floor, keeping it flexed, then return to rest. It was asked to repeat the movement 30 times with minimum effort (1st rep), 30 times with medium effort (2nd rep) and the last 30 times at maximum effort (3rd rep), for a total of 90 repetitions.

Ten healthy participants were recruited (5 males and 5 females, age: 27.8 ± 2.9 y.o., height: 172.3 ± 8.6 cm, weight: 69.1 ± 10.1 kg). Each of them had to perform the whole protocol two times to monitor respectively right and left foot.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Each participant successfully completed the assigned exercises and the results of the two tasks are presented in this Section. Results of the ET from the pad were consistent with those from the BTS MOCAP. In case of T1, ET was equal to 61.9 ± 8.9 s for BTS MOCAP and to 65.2 ± 10.1 s for the pad. These values were averaged between the two feet. The RMSE value of the movement rate detected by the BTS system and the pad were computed for each participant during the execution of T2, performed with right and left foot. The results for the right foot, reported in Figure 2, demonstrated high similarity between the BTS MOCAP and the pad (median RMSE below 0.2 Hz), independently on the level of effort (e.g. different repetitions in the legend). Similar results (not reported for the sake of brevity) were obtained for the left foot. These findings indicate a good consistency in the accuracy values of the pad compared to the measurements from the BTS MOCAP.

Fig. 2. RMSE value of the movement rate detected by the BTS MOCAP system and the sensorized pad for each participants during T2 with right foot.

For task T1, the most prominent variation in the CoP trajectory was expected to occur along the direction of the weight shifting, i.e. along the antero-poster axis. Indeed, there were no relevant changes in the signal in other directions. The variation in the CoP position was calculated for the two systems and resulted for the right foot in a value of 13.9 ± 1.3 cm and 7.4 ± 0.9 cm for the BTS MOCAP and the sensorized pad, respectively. For the left foot values of 13.8 ± 1.4 cm and 8.2 ± 1.8 cm were obtained.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The validation of the novel contactless motion monitoring system designed for motor tasks of elderly people during home-based rehabilitation has shown promising results. By employing a BTS MOCAP system as a benchmarking device, we ensured a reliable comparative analysis of the system performance.

All participants completed the assigned tasks easily, thus indicating that the system is user-friendly and suitable for its target use. The analysis of metrics such as RMSE and CoP allowed for a useful evaluation of motion features, as a starting point for further investigations. The sensorized pad demonstrated a performance consistent with the benchmarking device during realistic and relevant application conditions.

This study provides valuable insights for the perspective use of a contactless monitoring pad to support home-based exercises for the elderly people, promoting active aging, and potentially improving overall quality of life.

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